

A Study on the Oxidative Coupling of Thiourea with β -Naphthol and its Derivatives[†]

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β -Naphthol and some of its derivatives on oxidative coupling with thiourea in the presence of bromine or iodine gave bis-2-naphthol-1-sulphide as the major product along with some *S*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)isothiocarbamide as the product of coupling. Cyclic thiourea however gave the usual isothiocarbamide salt under identical conditions of reaction. A suitable mechanism of reaction has been suggested.

REACTIONS of thiourea¹ with pyrrole and indole yield *S*-(pyrrolyl)- and *S*-(3-indolyl)isothiuronium salts. Cyclic and acyclic thioureas similarly react with indole² giving *S*-(3-indolyl)isothiuronium salts. It was thought worthwhile to carry out this reaction with phenols.

In the present investigation reaction of thiourea with β -naphthol and its derivatives has been described. β -Naphthol, 1-bromo-2-naphthol and 2-naphthyl acetate, all yielded bis-2-naphthol-1-sulphide as the major product; a small amount of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthylisothiuronium salt was also obtained. The compounds were characterised through their spectral data, synthesis and products of oxidation etc. 2-Methoxynaphthalene and α -naphthol did not give any suitable product. In the case of 1-bromo-2-naphthol, debromination seems to be caused by thiourea and in the case of β -naphthyl acetate, deacetylation seems to be occurring through hydrolysis caused by the halogen acids formed during the reaction.

Cyclic thiourea, viz. ethelene thiourea, coupled with β -naphthol and gave only the isothiuronium compound.

Mechanism of reaction: The oxidation of thioureas with halogens has been known to give formamidine disulphide dihydrohalides³. A plausible mechanism of reaction based on an electrophilic attack of the sulphenyl cation⁴ obtained by the scission of the disulphide bond of the intermediate formamidine resulted into the coupling of the thiourea moiety ($X = \text{Br}$ or I) with β -naphthol giving isothiuronium compound [A]. Compound [A] in turn dismutates⁵ into the thiol.

The thiol subsequently can react either as (1) (this should explain the formation of small amount of elemental sulphur) or as (2).

[†] Part of the work was presented at International Conference on Heteroatom Chemistry, Kobe, Japan, 1987.

Ethelene thiourea coupled under identical conditions to give the isothiocarbamide

which seems to be more stable and is incapable of undergoing dismutation to a thiol, thereby providing an additional support to the above mechanism.

Experimental

General procedure: β -Naphthol (14.4 g, 0.1 mol) dissolved in methanol (25 ml) was added to the orange yellow solution of formamidine disulphide dihydrobromide (prepared *in situ* by reacting 7.6 g, 0.1 mol of thiourea suspended in 50 ml of methanol with 6 ml of bromine dissolved in 25 ml of methanol). Heat was evolved and a white solid of formamidine disulphide dihydrobromide resulted. The reaction mixture was stirred for 72 h at room temperature when the white solid formed slowly disappeared. The solution was filtered to remove the traces of sulphur and any unreacted formamidine disulphide dihydrohalide. Excess of the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The reaction mixture was set aside for 2–3 days. The resulting white crystalline solid (B) was filtered and washed with methanol several times. The filtrate was concentrated and worked up for the recovery of the soluble isothiocarbamide salt (A).

Bis-2-naphthol-1-sulphide (B) or bis-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)sulphide: It was recrystallised from ethanol as white crystals (60%), m.p. 228° (lit⁶, 217°) (Found: C, 75.52; H, 4.47; S, 10.2 calcd. for: C₂₀H₁₄O₂S: C, 75.47; H, 4.40; S, 10.05%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3335 (OH), 3040 (CH), 1590 (C=C), 1500 (Ar), 1205 (C–O) and 665 cm⁻¹ (C–S); δ (DMSO-d₆) 7.26–7.7 (6H, m), 7.95 (4H, d, ArH) and 8.8 (d, C₈-H and C₈-H). It did not give the characteristic test of thiols. It was soluble in NaOH (reprecipitated by the addition of dilute HCl), in dimethyl sulphoxide, benzene and hot methanol and insoluble in water and diethyl ether. A large (*M*+2) peak in mass spectrum showed the presence of one sulphur atom with mass (*M*⁺ peak) which corresponds to formula C₂₀H₁₄O₂S.

Acetyl derivative of (B): It had m.p. 196° (lit⁶, 200°) (Found: S, 8.1. C₂₄H₁₈O₄S calcd. for: S, 7.96%); δ (DMSO-d₆) 8.35 (2H, t), 6.76 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C₃-H and C₃-H), 7.0–7.65 (6H, m, ArH) and 1.46 (6H, s, CH₃).

Benzoyl derivative of (B): It had m.p. 208° (lit⁶, 206°) (Found: S, 6.15. C₂₄H₂₂O₄S calcd. for: S, 6.0%); δ (DMSO-d₆) 8.05 (2H, dd, *J* 9 Hz and 3 Hz, C₃-H and C₈-H) and 6.86–7.7 (20H, m, ArH).

Oxidation of (B) to dehydro-2-naphthyl-1-sulphide: Compound-B (0.1 mol) dissolved in 10% NaOH (10 ml) on oxidation with alkaline 10% potassium ferricyanide (5 ml), gave orange-red coloured solid which was washed with water and recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture, (60%), m.p. 154° (Found: S, 10.44. C₉H₁₂O₂S calcd. for: S, 10.12%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3050 (CH), 1680 (C=O), 1590 (C=C), 1510 (aromatic ring), 1235 (aromatic ethers) and 680 cm⁻¹ (C–S); δ (DMSO-d₆) 6.0 (1H, d, *J*_{3,4} 10 Hz, C₃-H) and 7.7–6.8 (11H, m, olefinic proton C₄-H and ArH).

S-(2-Hydroxy-1-naphthyl)isothiuronium bromide (A): The filtrate of the reaction mixture after isolation of (B) was concentrated under reduced pressure. Dry diethyl ether (50 ml) was then added to it and kept in a freezing mixture when white crystalline needles of (A) separated out. Its tlc with chloroform-methanol (19:1) gave a single spot. The product was recrystallised from methanol-diethyl ether mixture as white needles (20%), m.p. 146° (Found: C, 43.6; H, 3.9; N, 9.0; S, 11.0; Br, 26.4. C₁₁H₁₁ON₂SBr calcd. for: C, 44.1; H, 3.67; N, 9.36; S, 10.7; Br, 26.75%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3350 (OH), 3240 (NH), 2710 (NH₂ charged amine), 1625 (C=N and C=C), 1205 (C=O) and 675 cm⁻¹ (C–S); δ (DMSO-d₆) 6.7–7.6 (6H, m, aromatic CH), 7.7–8.6 (4H, br m, isothiuronium NH) and 6.2 (1H, s, C₂OH).

Hydrolysis of (B) to naphtho[1,2-d]-1,3-oxathiol-2-one: Compound-B (0.01 mol) suspended in a mixture of 2 N HCl (10 ml) and acetic acid (10 ml) was heated for 5 h on a water-bath. It was then poured into ice-cold water. The resulting brown coloured needles were recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, (25%), m.p. 104° (Found: C, 65.6; H 3.0; S, 16.1. C₁₁H₆SO₂ calcd. for: C, 65.34; H, 2.97; S, 15.84%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3050 (CH), 1745 (C=O), 1615 (C=C), 1505 (aromatic ring) and 715 cm⁻¹ (C–S); δ (DMSO-d₆) 7.5–8.2 (6H, m, ArH).

Oxidation of (A): Compound-A was oxidised by dilute sodium hydroxide and hydrogen peroxide or iodine to bis-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)disulphide (50%) through the intermediate thiol, m.p. 172° (Found: S, 18.5. C₂₀H₁₄S₂O₂ calcd. for: S, 18.28%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3440 (OH), 3040 (CH), 1590 (C=C), 1505 (ArH), 1175 (C–O) and 665 cm⁻¹ (C–S); δ (DMSO-d₆) 6.5–7.4 (12H, m, aromatic CH), 9.26 (2H, s, C₂OH and C₂OH).

Acknowledgement

Three of the authors (G.L.S., A.S. and U.G.) thank U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial support.

References

1. R. L. N. HARRIS, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1963, 4045; 1969, 4465.
2. K. NAGARAJAN, V. P. ARYA, T. N. PARTHASARATHY, S. J. SHENOY, R. K. SHAH and Y. S. KULKARNI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, 20, 672.

3. A. WERNER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 2166, 2180 ; R. FICHTER and W. WENK, *Chem. Ber.*, 1912, **45**, 1373 ; R. FICHTER and I. BRAUN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1914, **47**, 1526.
4. P. K. SRIVASTAVA and Y. R. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 803 ; P. K. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, **1**, 3434 ; 1964, **2**, 154 ; P. K. SRIVASTAVA and M. SALEAM, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1963, 2725 ; P. KLATSMANVI-GABOR, T. MEISEL and L. ERDEY, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1964, **40**, 99.
5. A. R. SURREY and H. G. LINDWALL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 1687 ; R. G. WOODBRIDGE and G. DOUGHERTY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4320.
6. H. A. STEVENSON and S. SMILES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1740